

Sociocultural and Economic Barriers to Female Decision Making Power in Dir (Lower)

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Abstract

Pakistan follows a patriarchal family system, and women decision making power within home remains a critical yet neglected dimension of gender equality, because men are typically head of the family. Although women constitute more than 50 percent of Pakistan's population, men dominate all walks of life. This study is designed to investigate the socio-cultural and economic barriers that limit women decision making power at household level in Dir Lower, with a specific focus on Tehsil Timergara. Women in Pakistan face many social and cultural problems in order to live a good life and achieve their legitimate rights.

The main reason for male dominance is the patriarchal family system throughout the country. Empowering women is the fundamental key to social, cultural, economic, political and educational development so that they can enjoy freedom within their legitimate rights. Thus the study highlights the relationship between dependent variable (female decision making in familial affairs) and independent variable (sociocultural and economic barriers). In this study quantitative research design was employed and Univariate and Bivariate including Chi Square test was carried out to assess the association between independent and dependent variable by using SPSS Version 21. The present study was conducted in Tehsil Timergara. Purposive sampling technique was used for data collection. The data were obtained from 379 respondents through structured interview schedule due to low literacy levels among the respondents. The study revealed that socio-cultural and economic barrier has significant association with female decision making power in familial affairs. This was true since the patriarchy, early marriage, economic dependency, lack of education, societal pressure and limited mobility was found significant association ($p=0.000$) with women decision making power in familial affairs.

Key Words: Socio-Cultural, Economic Barriers, Empowerment, Decision Making Power

INTRODUCTION

Women play important role in the advancement and development of state. However, women's involvement in various spheres of life is still lagging. Women are confined within the four walls of their homes and are considered and treated as inferior to men. Women are given less weight than men in decision making process. The importance of family decisions varies throughout a person's life. For example, choosing a partner is undoubtedly a big decision that should not be taken lightly, but it is rare for a couple to live happily ever after (Parpa., 2019; Kiani, 2012;

Jafree et al., 2020; Sultan, 2011). Kogame et al. (2020) highlighted that the psychological processes that result from selective activities among alternatives can be seen as the outcomes of decision-making. The process of decisions making results in options where the outcome can take the form of an action or opinion (Ferdoos & Zahra, 2016; Ali & Sultana, 2011). Gender inequality is a persistent feature of Pakhtun society's sociocultural values and norms. Gender discrimination is common in homes. Due to their socio-cultural, political and economic status, Pashtun women are completely trapped in a cycle of dependence and subordination (Ali & Sultana, 2011; Jafree et al., 2020). People have long held the belief that women are less knowledgeable and capable than men when it comes to social values regarding women's abilities (Khan et al., 2015; Rani et al., 2025). Despite this, women play significant role as men in the development of their countries (Jan, 2008). Through the socialization process, women who care for family members influence the socio cultural knowledge to their offspring. Children acquire their values and attitudes from their mothers. Therefore, in the contemporary context of modernity and development, women are agents of change not only in the home but also in society (Bhutta, & Haider2013; Sultana, 2011; Nussbaum, 2014).

The gender status of men and women determines their roles in the division of labor and decision-making patterns within the household. One of the key aspects of the husband and wife's relationship inside the family is the gender role. Distinguishing between risks, known possibilities, and uncertainties is a key challenge in seeking choices amidst uncertainty because indecision disturbs stability (Nourani et al., 2019; Khan et al., 2015; Rani et al., 2025). Folbre (2019) stated that women's roles are limited to childrearing, domestic duties, and being subordinate to men. Women barely have access to resources and have little say in household decision-making. Male family members make important decisions in women's lives, such as marriage, employment, education, shopping, family planning, and children's education (Ferdoos & Zahra, 2016).

Belay et al. (2016) stated that women's inferior status in household roles is reflected in low educational achievement, high illiteracy rate, minimal participation in political and financial activities and limited skill development opportunities. In the sociocultural, political, economic and legal spheres of life, women are perceived as inferior to men and occupy a subordinate position. According to sultana et al. (2010), women have less influence over decisions that affect their lives. Women were exploited and oppressed through prevailing religious and cultural traditions (Albader, 2020; Abera et al., 2020).

The male-dominated framework of Pakistani society seeks to subjugate women on every front. Women do not have the same access to employment, healthcare, or decision-making power as men, and even they are denied the basic right to education. However, young girls are expected to perform traditional gender role such as cleaning the house and washing dishes and clothes. Women are not treated with the respect they deserve at work place (Ali, 2022 & Ali et al., 2010; Bhutta, & Haider2013; Sultana, 2011). According to Perveen (2016), the 1973 charter of the Islamic republic of Pakistan grants women equal rights to men. Women have legal protection and security under basic human rights but implementation of legal rights are not always equal. Many of these legislative guarantees are blatantly ignored in almost every aspect of daily life (Hassan, 2020). Gender bias exists everywhere in the world. Women are generally treated harshly in Pakistan. Their development in civilized society is delayed for various reasons. In terms of numbers, Pakistani women and men are almost equal (Andrew David, 2025). Pakistani women

live in diverse areas. Families rarely witness the deceit of this system and disown this fake marriage. If they did, it would be very difficult for them to remarry their daughter. They are just as concealed as men. Additionally, families can trade, sell, or exchange these fake wedding permits (Bhutta, & Haider2013; Sultana, 2011; Jafree et al., 2020).

The process that gives people the ability to control their own lives within their social circles is known as empowerment. When people are free to take advantage of the legal opportunities that are available to them without any unnecessary restrictions, they are said to be empowered. For example, individuals should have continued access to options such as education, healthcare, professional development, personal decision-making and lifestyle shaping (Pratto, 2016; Khan et al., 2015; Rani et al., 2025). Therefore, empowerment involves the fight to improve the socioeconomic status of women through training, women's rights activism and collective actions, and education. Furthermore, women's empowerment can also be defined as allowing them to participate in tools and group decision-making processes to solve social problems. However, women's empowerment is also a process that allows women to change traditional and unfair gender roles so that they can gain the ability to choose from different options (Stromquist et al., 2015). To put it another way, "empowerment is not about giving people power because people already have enough power within their own treasury of enthusiasm and knowledge to perform their jobs brilliantly." Consequently, empowerment involves release of inherent power (Jaras et al., 2025). A widespread pattern of kinship in various regions of South Asia, the Middle East, and some African communities is the joint family system. Several generations of family members, including parents, children, and their descendants, such as grandparents, uncles, aunts, and cousins, live under the same roof and share resources and labor (Abbasi-Shavazi et al., 2025). This system is deeply embedded in religious and cultural traditions that place great importance on clan loyalty, collectivism, and respect for elders. Apart from institutionalizing patriarchy and gender power relations that affect women's autonomy and rights, the joint family system can provide social and economic security (Tamez et al., 2025).

Strict social expectations and patriarchal norms limit women's autonomy and decision-making power in these traditional joint-family households (Ali, 2022). Older men have the ability to make independent decisions on social, economic, and personal matters. Older men, especially fathers or grandfathers, often hold most of the authority in these households, controlling social interactions, family choices, and finances. While daughters-in-law are specifically given the status of brides to their sons, which forces them to adhere to traditional gender norms and prevents them from participating in economic and decision-making processes (Ali et al., 2010; Bhutta, & Haider, 2013; Sultana, 2011; Abdullah, 2024). Women married in joint families have less autonomy in personal and household decision-making than women married in nuclear families (Hameed et al., 2025).

Similarly, restricted mobility is the most prevalent limitation on women's liberty in joint family system. However, many women face social and cultural barriers that prevent them from traveling alone for pursuing higher education, or working in a formal job away from home without a man's consent. (Siwale & Mwalemba, 2023; Sanderson, 2014). This limited freedom results dependency on their male relatives, which significantly limits their access to various economic and educational options (Ferdoos & Zahra, 2016).

Female participation in the workforce is low in societies where the extended family is dominant because gendered division of labor norms still exist. Women are more constrained by economic dependence because male elders maintain financial power within the family, limiting women's access to income and their ability to make decisions about their resources (Das Gupta, 2010; Hora, 2014). Another major barrier to women's independence in joint family situations is financial hardship. Women's financial independence is limited because men in the family often handle financial resources (Kabeer, 2000). Many unemployed women do not make financial decisions on their own, which puts them at financial risk (Siwale & Mwalemba, 2023).

Methodology

The research focuses on to identify various socio-cultural and economic constraints to female decision making power in familial affairs in Pakhtun society. This research study was conducted in Tehsil Timergara, Dir (L). Purposive sampling technique was used for data collection. The data were obtained from 379 respondents through structured interview schedule due to low literacy levels among the respondents. Univariate and Bivariate including Chi Square test was carried out to assess the association between independent and dependent variable by using SPSS Version 21.

Table No. 1: Frequency and percentage distribution of sociocultural-economic barriers to female decision making power in family affairs

Statement	Yes	No	Don't know
Early marriage is the reasons for women's lack of decision-making power.	290(76.5%)	88(23.2%)	1(.3%)
Women in your family avoid expressing their opinions.	247(65.2%)	132(34.8%)	0.00(0.00)
Patriarchy reduces female decision making power in family affairs.	282(74.4%)	96(25.3%)	1(.3%)
Economic dependence lessens female decision-making power.	257(67.6%)	122(32.2%)	0.00(0.00)
Cultural and traditions limit women's role in decision-making power.	209(55.1%)	169(44.6%)	1(.3%)
Lack of education limits women's decision-making power.	297(78.4%)	82(21.6%)	0.00(0.00)
Men are considered the primary decision makers in your family.	225(59.4%)	154(40.6%)	0.00(0.00)
Restrictions on female external mobility limit their decision-making power.	262(69.1%)	117(30.9%)	0.00(0.00)

Societal Pressure discourage female decision making power in family affair	235(62.0%)	144(38.0%)	0.00(0.00)
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Explanation

Table no 1 presents differing associations between socio-economic barriers to women decision making power in familial affairs. The table shows the agreement of 290 (76.5%) of the respondents to the perception that early marriage is the reasons for women's lack of decision-making power, While 88 (23.2%) of the respondents were not agreed with this statement, and 1 (0.3%) having no information about it. This statement is supported by the findings of McDougal et al., (2018) and Abera et al., (2020) that that early marriage is the reasons for women's lack of decision-making power. Similarly the findings of Wahyuningsih et al., (2025) also supported the above statement.

Moreover, the table further illustrates that 247 (65.2%) of the respondents deduced that women avoid expressing their opinions in family affairs, Whereas 132 (34.8%) oppose the statement. The statement finds its endorsement in the conclusions of Miedema et al., (2020), Sultana (2011) and Stark (2018) that in many cases women avoid to express their opinion in family affairs. They even don't give their consent to marriage because of limited or no choice at all.

Furthermore, the table presents that 282 (74.4%) of the respondents had concurrence with the perception that patriarchy reduces female decision making power in family affairs, while 96 (25.3%) were not agree to the above statement and 1 (0.3%) of the respondents had no comprehension of the statement. the statement has been corroborated by the findings of Ferdoos & Zahra (2016), Sultana(2011) and Zuo and Bian (2005) that patriarchy limits female decision making power.

Moreover, the study further demonstrates the approbation of 257 (67.6%) of the respondents of the statement that, economic dependence lessens female decision-making power, while 122 (32.2%) of the respondents negate the above statement. This statement has been endorsed by the conclusions of Bhutta, & Haider (2013), Sultana (2011), Kushwah (2015) and Balabanova (2007), which stated that economic dependence lessens female decision-making power.

The table further showed, that 209 (55.1%) of the respondents believed that cultural and traditions limit women's role in decision-making power. Despite the fact that 169 (44.6%) were not agree to the above statement. The statement finds its endorsement in the conclusions of Ali & Sultana (1999), Sultana (2011), Khan et al., (2015) and Rani et al., (2025) highlighted that economic dependence lessens female decision-making power.

Moreover, the table demonstrates that 297 (78.4%) of the respondents believe that lack of education limits women's decision-making power, whereas 82 (21.6%) of the respondents repudiated this statement. This statement has been aided by the findings of Jan (2008), Sultana (2011), Agnihotri (2021), Hora (2014) and Elderred et al., (2014) that lack of education limits women's decision-making power.

Furthermore, majority of respondent 225 (59.4%) revealed that men are considered the primary decision makers in your family, whereas 154 (40.6%) disaffirmed the statement. This statement has been attributed by the findings of Jafree et al., (2020), Sultan (2011), Ferdoos & Zahra (2016), Ali & Sultana (2011) and Zuo and Bian (2005) stated that that men are considered the primary decision makers in familial affairs. Moreover, it is demonstrated in the table 262

(69.1%) believes that that restrictions on female external mobility limit their decision-making power, while 117 (30.9%) of the respondents debunked the above statement. This statement is supported by the conclusions drawn by Chapagain (2015), Ferdous & Uddin (2021), Ali & Sultana (1999) and Jafree et al., (2020).

The table further presents that 235 (62.0%) agreed with the statement that societal pressure discourage female decision making power in family affair, while 144 (38.0%) rejected the above statement. This statement is also supported by the findings of Eagly (1983), Siwale & Mwalemba (2023), Carli (2001) and Sultana (2011).

Table No. 2: Bi- variate analysis of socio-economic barriers and familial affairs

Statement	Chi square χ^2 / P value
Early marriage is the reasons for women's lack of decision-making power	$\chi^2=46.875(p=0.000)$
Women in your family avoid expressing their opinions.	$\chi^2=5.737(p=0.057)$
Patriarchy reduces female decision making power in family affairs.	$\chi^2=51.103(p=0.000)$
Economic dependence lessens female decision-making power.	$\chi^2=7.574 (p=0.023)$
Cultural and traditions limit women's role in decision-making power.	$\chi^2=10.783 (p=0.029)$
Lack of education limits women's decision-making power.	$\chi^2=27.622(p=0.000)$
Men are considered the primary decision makers in your family.	$\chi^2=6.403(p=0.041)$
Restrictions on female external mobility limit their decision-making power.	$\chi^2=9.934(p=0.007)$
Societal Pressure discourage female decision making power in family affairs	$\chi^2=2.201(p=0.333)$

Explanation

The data presented in table 2 encompasses the association between the socio-economic barriers and female decision making power in familial affairs. The study exhibits that a highly significant association ($p=0.000$) was found between early marriage and female decision making in family affairs. The study further shows the presence of a significant association ($p=0.057$) was found between respondents perception that women in your family avoid expressing their opinions with female decision making power in familial affairs. Ensuingly, the table shows that a highly significant ($p=0.000$) association was found between patriarchy with female decision making in familial affair. Furthermore, the study examines the respondent’s perception between economic dependence lessens female decision-making power. The table shows a significant

association ($p=0.023$) existed between economic dependence lessens female decision-making power in familial affairs. The study further shows the respondents perception regarding cultural and traditions limit women's role in decision-making power. Subsequently, the table exhibits the presence of a significant association ($p=0.029$) while determining the relationship between cultural and traditions limit women's role in decision-making power in familial affairs. The respondents further revealed that lack of education limits women's decision was found highly statistically significant ($p=0.000$). The study further exhibits that a significant association ($p=0.014$) was found between men are considered the primary decision makers in your family and female decision making power. Restrictions on female external mobility limit their decision-making power was also found statistically significant ($p=0.007$). Subsequently, the table exhibits the no significant association ($p=0.333$) while determining the relationship between Societal Pressure discourage female decision making.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concluded that women are discriminated in all spheres of life, including family matters, which hinders their decision-making power and empowerment. Generally women are not provided equal opportunity like males such as education and Jobs due to unnecessary cultural taboos. Thus women are economically dependent on their male counterparts. There is male dominance and role of women in the domestic setting are not harmonious. Limitations on women's active participation and mobility further alleviate her voice in decision-making. The study revealed that socio-cultural and economic barrier has significant association with female decision making power in familial affairs. This was true since the patriarchy, early marriage, economic dependency, lack of education, societal pressure and limited mobility was found significant association with women decision making power in familial affairs. Proper educational facilities should be provided for females without discrimination in the targeted area. Govt. must facilitate women to make better use of their productive capabilities in different fields. Media should play his role in promoting importance of women empowerment regarding their decision making in family matters.

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